

Cyclic voltammetric and electronic absorption spectral investigations on binary and mixed-ligand copper(II) complexes with diethyldithiocarbamate and diimines[†]

Krishna Srivastava*, Ved Prakash, Sandeep Kumar Singh and Jagdish Prasad

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dr_krishna_s@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 05 March 2012, accepted 12 March 2012

Abstract : The electrochemical properties of binary and mixed-ligand Cu^{II} complexes involving diethyldithiocarbamate (Et₂-dtc⁻) as primary ligand and 2,2'-bipyridine/1,10-phenanthroline (bipy/phen) as coligands formed in different Cu^{II} : Et₂-dtc : bipy/phen molar ratios in acetone solution have been studied by using cyclic voltammetry. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in acetone solution containing 0.2 M NaClO₄ as a supporting electrolyte at a platinum working electrode. On the basis of CV results, it is concluded that there are two complex species present in equilibrium in solution in mixed-ligand Cu^{II} : Et₂-dtc : bipy/phen (1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratios) systems. It is noteworthy that binary Cu^{II}(Et₂-dtc)_{1 or 2} and mixed-ligand Cu^{II}(Et₂-dtc)(bipy/phen) complex species exhibit both oxidation (Cu^{2+/3+}) and reduction (Cu^{2+/+}) processes while binary Cu^{II}(bipy/phen)_{1 or 2} complex species show only Cu^{2+/+} redox change. UV-Visible spectra of the above systems have also been studied in acetone.

Keywords : Cyclic voltammetry, diethyldithiocarbamate, bipyridine, phenanthroline, copper(II) complexes.

1. Introduction

Dithiocarbamates are a large family of compounds that have been widely investigated because they are of great interest in different fields. Many studies have been carried out in order to gain information on the complexes formed by dithiocarbamates and metal ions, which are used as fungicides and pesticides such as Ziram and Thiram¹. Their range of applications covers several uses in chemical industries, biology, and biochemistry. For example, some of the dialkyl-substituted dithiocarbamate salts have also shown interesting biological effects, which include antialkylation^{2,3} or anti-HIV properties^{4,5}. They are also used as effective antidotes for cadmium intoxication^{6,7}. Dithiocarbamate forms a chelate with virtually all transition metal ions⁸. The bidentate anion is also known to bridge two transition metal centers⁹. Water-soluble dialkyldithiocarbamate complexes have been tested in various medical applications^{10,11}. The substituent effect for the one electron oxidation and reduction for Cu(R₂-dtc)₂ at the platinum electrode was recorded by Chant *et al.*¹². Dithiocarbamate ligands have stabilizing ability towards Cu²⁺ and their Cu^{II} complexes undergo reversible

oxidation (Cu^{2+/3+}) and reduction processes (Cu^{2+/+}) to their monocation and monoanion, respectively¹³. Prasad and coworkers have also reported¹⁴ the CV behaviours of Cu^{II,III}-diethyldithiocarbamate/morpholine-dithiocarbamate complexes.

In the present paper the spectral (UV-Visible) and electrochemical behaviours of binary and mixed-ligand Cu^{II} complexes of diethyldithiocarbamate and bipy/phen formed in different molar ratios (1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1) of Cu^{II} : Et₂-dtc : bipy/phen have been reported. The structures of the ligands taken in the present investigation are shown below :

2. Experimental

Copper perchlorate hexahydrate (Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O),

[†]In honour of Professor K. B. Pandeya on the occasion of his 70th Birth Anniversary.

sodium diethyldithiocarbamate and diimine (bipy and phen) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Private Ltd. and A.R. grade acetone was procured from E. Merck India Ltd. and were used as such. The CV measurements were performed on BAS Electrochemical System Model EPSILON. The auxiliary electrode was a platinum wire and reference electrode was Ag/AgCl in saturated KCl ($E^0 = +199$ mV vs NHE). Purging and blanketing of nitrogen (99.99% pure) was done for analyte solution placed in the electrochemical cell of 15 mL capacity for 20 min. Room temperature electronic absorption spectra of complexes in different molar ratios in acetone were measured in the range 1000–250 nm with a Perkin-Elmer UV-Visible spectrophotometer Model Lambda 35 available in our laboratory. 1 mM solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in acetone was used in both the binary and mixed-ligand complexes. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in acetone containing 0.2 M NaClO_4 as a supporting electrolyte at a platinum working electrode at 25 ± 0.5 °C.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electrochemical behaviours of binary copper(II)-diethyldithiocarbamate complexes formed in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios

CV results of binary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{Et}_2\text{-dtc}$ complex species formed in 1 : 1 (green) and 1 : 2 (red-brown) molar ratios in acetone solution are summarized in Table 1 and the CV is displayed in 1 : 2 molar ratio at 100 mV s^{-1} in Fig. 1(a). It should be mentioned initially that diethyldithiocarbamate ligand in acetone is irreversibly oxidized to disulphide with peak potential +63 to +107 mV vs Ag/AgCl in the scan rate range 25–1000 mV s^{-1} (Fig. 1(b)) while bipy and phen are electro-inactive in the potential range studied (+1300 to –850 mV vs Ag/AgCl).

A positive scan initiated from 0.0 V in the potential limits –50 to +900 mV vs Ag/AgCl showed an oxidation couple corresponding to $\text{Cu}^{2+/3+}$ with formal potential, $E^{0'} \approx +501$ mV and a reduction couple ascribed to $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ with $E^{0'} \approx -521$ mV in 1 : 2 molar ratio at 100 mV s^{-1} (Table 1 and Fig. 1(a)). The coulometric experiments performed at constant potential of +700 mV and –800 mV have shown the involvement of one electron per molecule of the complex, both for oxidation ($\text{Cu}^{2+/3+}$) and reduction ($\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$) processes. Furthermore, the plot

of I_{pc_1} or I_{pc_2} vs square root of scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) gives a straight line without any intercept at slow scan rate (up to 500 mV s^{-1}), indicating that the redox processes are diffusion-controlled. Also, the $\Delta E_p (= E_{\text{pa}} - E_{\text{pc}})$ values are greater than 60 mV value for reversible one electron transfer, showing that redox reactions are quasi-reversible. It should be mentioned that the peak current ratio ($I_{\text{pc}_1}/I_{\text{pa}_1}$) for the oxidation couple ($\text{Cu}^{2+/3+}$) is 1.0 at all scan rates studied, showing that the electron transfer occurs without any chemical complication (Table 1). However, the peak current ratio ($I_{\text{pa}_2}/I_{\text{pc}_2}$) for the second redox process is less than unity (Table 1), clearly indicating that the electron transfer is followed by a chemical reaction (EC mechanism¹⁵). It may be noted that in 1 : 1 molar ratio the peak current ratio ($I_{\text{pc}_1}/I_{\text{pa}_1}$) is > 1.0 , indicating that adsorption occurs in ($\text{Cu}^{2+/3+}$) process while in ($\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$) reduction process anodic peak does not appear (Table 1), showing that the $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}\text{-Et}_2\text{dtc}$ species is not stable in the time-window of the CV experiments.

3.2. Electrochemical behaviours of binary copper(II)-bipy/phen complexes formed in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios

The electrochemical behaviour of binary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{bipy/phen}$ complexes formed in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios have also been studied for comparison. The CV data for these systems are given in Table 2 and cyclic voltammograms for $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{phen}$ system in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios are displayed in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b), respectively.

Cyclic voltammograms of binary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{bipy}$ complex formed in 1 : 1 metal to ligand molar ratio displayed one reduction peak in the forward scan while in the reverse scan a stripping anodic peak was observed. The binary $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}\text{-bipy}$ complex species is unstable under the time-window of the CV experiments and undergoes disproportionation reaction into Cu^0 and $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ and the stripping anodic peak is due to demetallation of copper deposited on the surface of electrode into Cu^{II} . CVs show diffusion-controlled single-electron quasi-reversible couple (c_1/a_1) with formal potential, $E^{0'} = +235$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 78$ mV and $I_{\text{pa}_1}/I_{\text{pc}_1} = 0.7$ (at 100 mV s^{-1}) in addition to an anodic peak at $E_{\text{pa}_1'} = +508$ mV in the reverse scan (Table 2), clearly showing that electron transfer is followed by a chemical reaction¹⁵ at the reduction step c_1

Fig. 1. CVs of binary Cu^{II} complex species in 1 : 2 Cu-Et₂dtc system (a), and Et₂dtc ligand (b), in acetone containing 0.2 M NaClO₄ at 100 mV s⁻¹.

Table 1. CV data for binary Cu^{II}-Et₂dtc complex species formed in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal-ligand molar ratios in acetone/0.2 M NaClO₄ medium

Cu ^{II} : Et ₂ dtc molar ratio	Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{pa₁} (mV)	E _{pc₁} (mV)	E ⁰ (1) (mV)	ΔE _p (1) (mV)	I _{pc₁} /I _{pa₁}	E _{pc₂} (mV)	E _{pa₂} (mV)	E ⁰ (2) (mV)	ΔE _p (2) (mV)	I _{pa₂} /I _{pc₂}
1 : 1 (Dark green solution)	25	542	450	496	92	1.2	-574	NA			
	50	544	446	495	98	1.2	-576	NA			
	100	546	444	495	102	1.1	-579	NA			
	200	548	444	496	104	1.1	-586	NA			
	300	548	444	496	104	1.1	-588	NA			
	400	550	444	497	106	1.1	-590	NA			
1 : 2 (Dark brown solution)	500	552	444	498	108	1.1	-592	NA			
	25	537	467	502	70	1.0	-558	-488	-523	70	0.7
	50	537	465	501	72	1.0	-560	-482	-521	78	0.6
	100	538	464	501	74	1.0	-562	-480	-521	82	0.5
	200	540	464	502	76	1.0	-570	-478	-524	92	0.6
	300	540	462	501	78	1.0	-570	-476	-523	94	0.6
	400	541	463	502	78	1.0	-574	-474	-524	100	0.5
500	541	463	502	78	1.0	-580	-472	-526	108	0.6	

NA = Not Appeared.

Table 2. CV data for binary Cu^{II}-bipy/phen complex species formed in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal-ligand molar ratios in acetone/0.2 M NaClO₄ medium

Cu ^{II} : diimine molar ratio	Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{pc₁} (mV)	E _{pa₁} (mV)	E ⁰ (1) (mV)	ΔE _p (1) (mV)	I _{pa₁} /I _{pc₁}	E _{pa₁'} (mV)	I _{pa₁'} (μA)
Cu ^{II} : bipy	25	200	268	234	68	0.8	508	1.1
1 : 1 (Blue solution)	50	198	272	235	74	0.8	499	1.5
	100	196	274	235	78	0.7	508	2.5
	200	194	276	235	82	0.6	531	4.5

Table-2 (contd.)

	300	194	278	236	84	0.6	538	6.5
	400	192	280	236	88	0.6	550	8.4
	500	192	282	237	90	0.6	556	9.8
1 : 2	25	114	172	143	58	1.0	NA	
(Blue solution)	50	112	174	143	62	1.0	NA	
	100	108	174	141	66	1.0	NA	
	200	106	176	141	70	0.9	NA	
	300	104	178	141	74	0.9	NA	
	400	104	178	141	74	0.9	NA	
	500	102	180	141	78	0.9	NA	
Cu ^{II} : phen	25	220	282	251	62	0.80	334	21.5
1 : 1	50	220	286	253	66	0.78	345	16.9
(Blue solution)	100	218	288	253	70	0.78	355	14.4
	200	218	292	255	74	0.70	483	9.2
	300	216	296	256	80	0.70	491	14.4
	400	214	300	257	86	0.70	503	19.5
	500	210	302	256	92	0.80	516	24.8
	600	206	306	256	100	0.80	523	30.1
1 : 2	25	208	272	240	64	1.0	NA	
(Blue solution)	50	206	274	240	68	1.0	NA	
	100	205	277	241	72	1.0	NA	
	200	204	282	243	78	0.9	NA	
	300	202	284	243	82	0.8	NA	
	400	201	285	243	84	0.8	NA	
	500	196	286	241	90	0.8	NA	

NA = Not Appeared.

Fig. 2. CVs of binary Cu^{II} complex species in 1 : 1 Cu-phen system (a) at 1000 mV s⁻¹ and 1 : 2 molar ratios (b) at 100 mV s⁻¹ in acetone solution containing 0.2 M NaClO₄.

(EC mechanism). It should be noted that in Cu^{II}-bipy 1 : 2 molar ratio a diffusion-controlled single-electron quasi-reversible couple (c_1/a_1) is observed with $E^{0'} = +141$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 66$ mV and $I_{pa_1}/I_{pc_1} = 1.0$ at 100 mV s⁻¹ due to $[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})_2]^{2+}$ species in solution. However, the anodic peak a_1' did not appear.

It should be noted that electrochemical behaviour of Cu^{II} : phen complex is similar to that of Cu^{II} : bipy complex except that the reduction of Cu^{II} : phen complex is easier as compared to Cu^{II} : bipy complex due to stronger π -acceptor behaviour of phen as compared to bipy. Furthermore, the anodic peak E_{pa_1}' did not appear in the 1 : 2 molar ratio, showing that $[\text{CuL}_2]^{2+}$ complex species (L = bipy or phen) are stable. Furthermore, at higher scan rates (≥ 100 mV s⁻¹) a well defined quasi-reversible reduction couple with formal potential $E^{0'} \approx +253$ mV (at 1000 mV s⁻¹) with an additional irreversible oxidation peak at $E_{pa_1}' = +551$ mV was observed due to $\text{Cu}^0 \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} + 2e^-$ process in 1 : 1 Cu^{II}-phen system (Fig. 2(a)).

Also, the peak current ratio (I_{pa_1}/I_{pc_1}) is < 1.0 infers to EC mechanism¹⁵. It is interesting to note that in 1 : 2 molar ratio only a single quasi-reversible couple with $E^{0'} \approx +241$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 72$ mV and $I_{pa_1}/I_{pc_1} = 1.0$ is observed (Table 2 and Fig. 2(b)). A perusal of Table 2 clearly shows that the value of formal potential $E^{0'}$ of binary Cu^{II} : bipy/phen complex species becomes less positive in 1 : 2 molar ratio as compared to that in 1 : 1 molar ratio, indicating that the reduction of $[CuL_2]^{2+}$ (L = bipy or phen) is difficult as compared to that of $[CuL]^{2+}$ species in the given medium. The value of ΔE_p becomes smaller and also the peak current ratio is unity in 1 : 2 molar ratio, showing that the reduction of $[CuL_2]^{2+}$ species is more reversible without any chemical complication.

3.3. Electrochemical behaviours of Cu^{II} complex species in mixed-ligand Cu^{II} - Et_2dtc -bipy/phen systems

The electrochemical behaviours of complex species in mixed-ligand Cu^{II} - Et_2dtc -bipy/phen systems in 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratios have been studied in acetone/0.2 M $NaClO_4$ and the CV data are given in Tables 3–5 and CVs are displayed in Figs. 3–5, respectively.

3.3.1. Cu^{II} - Et_2dtc -bipy/phen 1 : 1 : 1 mixed-ligand systems

In the case of Cu^{II} - Et_2dtc -bipy 1 : 1 : 1 system, a positive scan in the potential range +150 to +1300 mV exhibited a quasi-reversible redox couple ($Cu^{2+/3+}$) with $E^{0'} = +519$ mV ($E_{pa_1} = 576$ mV, $E_{pc_1} = 462$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 114$ mV and $I_{pc_1}/I_{pa_1} = 0.6$) and a second irreversible anodic peak at more positive potential, $E_{pa_2} = +1009$ mV at 50 mV s^{-1} (Fig. 3(a)), while the negative potential scan in the potential limit +380 to -550 mV displayed a quasi-reversible redox couple ($Cu^{2+/+}$) with $E^{0'} = -114$ mV ($E_{pc_1'} = -188$ mV, $E_{pa_1'} = -40$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 148$ mV with current ratio ($I_{pa_1'}/I_{pc_1'} = 0.7$) as given in Table 3 and Fig. 3(b) at a scan rate 100 mV s^{-1} , clearly showing that oxidation/reduction processes involve EC mechanism¹⁵. On the basis of CV results, it may therefore be concluded that there are two complex species; $[Cu(Et_2dtc)(S)_2]^+$ (green coloured), **1** and $[Cu(Et_2dtc)-(bipy)(S)]^+$, **2** present in equilibrium in solution, where S is a solvent molecule coordinated through O atom. The first oxidation couple (a_1/c_1) may be ascribed to the oxidation of a binary Cu^{II} - Et_2dtc complex, **1** ($Cu^{2+/3+}$).

Table 3. CV data for complex species formed in Cu^{II} - Et_2dtc -bipy/phen : 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio in acetone/0.2 M $NaClO_4$ medium

Scan rate (mV s^{-1})	E_{pa_1} (mV)	E_{pc_1} (mV)	$E^{0'}(1)$ (mV)	$\Delta E_p(1)$ (mV)	I_{pc_1}/I_{pa_1}	E_{pa_2} (mV)	$E_{pc_1'}$ (mV)	$E_{pa_1'}$ (mV)	$E^{0'}(2)$ (mV)	$\Delta E_p(2)$ (mV)	$I_{pa_1'}/I_{pc_1'}$
Cu^{II}-Et_2dtc-bipy											
25	570	466	518	104	0.6	1006	-180	-50	-115	130	0.7
50	572	464	518	108	0.6	1009	-184	-48	-116	136	0.7
100	576	462	519	114	0.6	1010	-188	-40	-114	148	0.7
200	578	460	519	118	0.6	1010	-200	-30	-115	170	0.6
300	578	460	519	118	0.6	1012	-206	-24	-115	182	0.6
400	578	460	519	118	0.6	1012	-208	-22	-115	186	0.6
500	578	460	519	118	0.6	1014	-212	-20	-116	192	0.6
Cu^{II}-Et_2dtc-phen											
25	590	444	517	146	1.4	1025	-157	-87	-122	70	0.7
50	590	442	516	148	1.4	1020	-162	-86	-124	76	0.7
100	594	440	517	154	1.4	1020	-195	-85	-140	110	0.7
200	596	438	517	158	1.3	1024	-205	-85	-145	120	0.7
300	598	436	517	162	1.1	1025	-215	-85	-150	130	0.6
400	598	432	515	166	1.1	1025	-216	-84	-150	132	0.6
500	600	432	515	170	1.1	1025	-220	-80	-150	140	0.6
3000	709					1020 (944) ^a				76 ^b	0.3 ^c
5000	742					1022 (948) ^a				74 ^b	0.4 ^c
8000	770					1024 (950) ^a				74 ^b	0.4 ^c

^a E_{pc_1} values are given in parenthesis; ^b $\Delta E_p(2)$ values = $E_{pa_2} - E_{pc_2}$; ^c I_{pc_2}/I_{pa_2} values.

Fig. 3. CVs of complex species in 1 : 1 : 1 Cu-Et₂dtc-bipy system (a) at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹ and (b) at 100 mV s⁻¹ in acetone containing 0.2 M NaClO₄.

Furthermore, the second irreversible oxidation peak (*a*₂) and the redox couple (*c*₁'/*a*₁') are assigned to redox processes Cu^{2+/3+} and Cu^{2+/+}, respectively of the five coordinated mixed-ligand Cu^{II} complex **2**.

It is important to mention that in bipy mixed-ligand system the current ratio (*I*_{pc1}/*I*_{pa1}) is < 1.0, while in phen system it is > 1.0, indicating that the former involves

EC mechanism while the latter system involves adsorption of the oxidized species on the electrode surface.

3.3.2. Cu^{II}-Et₂dtc-bipy/phen 1 : 1 : 2 mixed-ligand systems

CV data for complex species present in Cu^{II} mixed-ligand system are given in Table 4 and the CVs are displayed in Fig. 4. CV results (Tables 4 and 2) clearly show that binary and mixed-ligand complexes **1** and **2**, respectively exist in equilibrium in the acetone medium.

Table 4. CV data for complex species formed in Cu^{II}-Et₂dtc-bipy/phen : 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio in acetone/0.2 M NaClO₄ medium

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pa_2} (mV)	E_{pc_2} (mV)	E_{pc_1} (mV)	E_{pa_1} (mV)	$E^{O'}(1)$ (mV)	$\Delta E_p(1)$ (mV)	I_{pa_1}/I_{pc_1}	$E_{pc_2'}$ (mV)	$I_{pc_2'}$ (μ A)
Cu ^{II} -Et ₂ dtc-bipy									
25	1010	NA	112	180	146	68		-195	2.0
50	1010	NA	109	183	146	74	1.0	-201	2.7
100	1015	NA	103	189	146	86	1.0	-201	3.1
200	1020	NA	94	196	145	104	1.0	-201	4.3
300	1020	NA	92	196	144	104	1.0	-201	5.9
400	1025	NA	86	204	145	117	1.0	-203	7.3
500	1025	NA	84	206	145	124	1.0	-204	8.3
1000	1030	NA	80	210	145	130	0.9	NA	
Cu ^{II} -Et ₂ dtc-phen									
25	1017	NA	209	275	242	66	0.6	-128	1.4
50	1021	NA	205	275	240	70	0.6	-134	2.0
100	1023	NA	204	280	242	76	0.6	-141	2.7
200	1028	NA	200	280	240	80	0.7	-154	3.8
300	1028	NA	195	285	240	90	1.1	-156	4.8
400	1028	NA	190	290	240	100	1.1	-162	5.4
500	1030	950	184	300	242	116	1.1	-162	5.4
600	1030	948	NA	NA				NA	
800	1030	946	NA	NA				NA	
1000	1030	945	NA	NA				NA	
3000	1030	940	NA	NA				NA	
5000	1030	940	NA	NA				NA	

NA = Not appeared.

Fig. 4. CV of Cu^{II} complex species in 1 : 1 : 2 Cu-Et₂dtc-bipy system at 500 mV s⁻¹ in acetone solution containing 0.2 M NaClO₄.

1
2

A positive scan in the potential range +600 to +1300

 mV vs Ag/AgCl showed a totally irreversible anodic peak ($E_{pa_2} = 1025$ mV) at 500 mV s⁻¹ due to oxidation of mixed-ligand complex **2**, while a negative scan in the

potential range from +700 to -500 mV exhibited a quasi-reversible $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ redox couple (c_1/a_1) with $E^{0'} = 146$ mV due to binary complex **1** (Tables 4 and 2). It is noteworthy that Cu^{II} mixed-ligand complexes involving bipy and phen show almost similar electrochemical behaviour except that phen mixed-ligand complex is comparatively more stable under the time-window of CV experiments which is seen in their cyclic voltammograms. The phen mixed-ligand complex exhibited a quasi-reversible redox couple, $\text{Cu}^{2+/3+}$ (a_2/c_2) at scan rate ≥ 500 mV s^{-1} involving EC mechanism ($I_{\text{pc}_2}/I_{\text{pa}_2} < 1$). On the other hand bipy-mixed-ligand complex exhibited a totally irreversible anodic peak in the scan rate studied (Table 4 and Fig. 4). The most probable reaction pathways involved in the redox processes are suggested below :

3.3.3. $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Et}_2\text{dtc-bipy/phen}$ 1 : 2 : 1 mixed-ligand systems

The CV data for complex species in 1 : 2 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Et}_2\text{dtc-phen}$ system is given in Table 5 and the CVs are shown in Fig. 5(a,b) at 100 mV s^{-1} . On the basis of CV results and UV-Visible spectrum, the following binary **1** and mixed-ligand complex species **2** seems to be in equilibrium in solution.

A positive scan in the potential limits 0 to 1300 mV showed a quasi-reversible $\text{Cu}^{2+/3+}$ redox couple (a_1/c_1) with $E^{0'}(1) = +499$ mV due to binary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Et}_2\text{dtc}$ complex **1** and the second quasi-reversible redox couple $\text{Cu}^{2+/3+}$ at $E_{\text{pa}_2} = +1044$ mV, $E_{\text{pc}_2} = 950$ mV, $E^{0'} = +997$ mV and $\Delta E_p = 94$ mV due to mixed-ligand com-

plex **2** (Table 5 and Fig. 5(a)). A negative scan exhibited one small reduction peak at $E_{\text{pc}_2''} = -154$ mV and a quasi-reversible reduction couple ($\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$) with $E_{\text{pc}_2'} = -572$ mV, $E_{\text{pa}_2'} = -470$ mV ($E^{0'}(3) \approx -521$ mV), $\Delta E_p = 102$ mV and $I_{\text{pa}_2'}/I_{\text{pc}_2'} \approx 0.4$ at 100 mV s^{-1} due to complex **1**. Similarly, the reduction peak $E_{\text{pc}_2''}$ is due to irreversible reduction of mixed-ligand complex **2**. The most probable mechanism may be given as :

The electrochemical behaviour of mixed-ligand complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{-dtc})(\text{bipy})]^+$ on the other hand is different than that of its phen analogue in two respects :

- (i) The formal potential, $E^{0'} = 472$ mV for the oxidation couple ($\text{Cu}^{2+/3+}$) corresponding to binary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Et}_2\text{-dtc}$ complex species is less positive (Table 5) as compared to that found for pure binary $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{-dtc})_2]$ system in 1 : 2 molar ratio (Table 1),
- (ii) the peak current ratio $I_{\text{pc}_1}/I_{\text{pa}_1} < 1.0$, and
- (iii) the redox process $\text{Cu}^{2+/3+}$ corresponding to mixed-ligand complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{-dtc})(\text{bipy})]^+$ is totally irreversible in the scan rate studied upto 1500 mV s^{-1} , while the phen analogue shows quasi-reversibility at scan rate ≥ 100 mV s^{-1} , clearly indicating that the oxidation of the mixed-ligand complex is followed by chemical reaction (EC mechanism)¹⁵.

It is noteworthy that the same mixed-ligand species $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})(\text{phen})(\text{A})]^+$ exists in 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 systems involving phen as secondary ligand because the magnitude of formal potential $E^{0'}$ remains almost invariant (Tables 3-5).

3.3.4. Electronic spectra

UV-Visible spectra of the binary $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{bipy/phen}$ complexes in acetone solution (1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios)

Table 5. CV data for complex species formed in Cu^{II}-Et₂dtc-bipy/phen systems in 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratio in acetone/0.2 M NaClO₄ medium

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pa_1} (mV)	E_{pc_1} (mV)	$E^0(1)$ (mV)	$\Delta E_p(1)$ (mV)	I_{pc_1}/I_{pa_1}	E_{pa_2} (mV)	I_{pa_2} (μ A)	E_{pc_2} (mV)	I_{pc_2} (μ A)	E_{pa_3} (mV)	$E^0(2)$ (mV)	$\Delta E_p(2)$ (mV)	I_{pa_3}/I_{pc_3}
Cu^{II}-Et₂dtc-bipy													
25	501	441	471	60	-	1010	12.5	NA	-	-490	-533	86	0.6
50	502	440	471	62	-	1010	15.0	NA	-	-488	-533	90	0.6
100	504	442	473	62	0.4	1016	17.6	-190	2.2	-486	533	94	0.6
200	504	442	473	62	0.4	1030	19.4	-201	4.7	-484	-533	98	0.5
300	504	442	473	62	0.4	1032	20.4	-204	5.6	-482	-533	102	0.5
400	504	440	472	64	0.4	1036	21.3	-208	6.5	-482	533	102	0.5
500	506	440	473	66	0.4	1043	22.0	-209	7.1	-480	-533	106	0.5
1500	514	424	469	90	0.4	1087	25.0	-230	10.4	-476	-535	118	0.4
Cu^{II}-Et₂dtc-phen													
							$\Delta E_p(2)$ (mV)						
25	530	466	498	64	1.0	1041		-150	1.6	-565		102	0.4
50	532	464	498	68	1.0	1042		-152	2.2	-569		120	0.4
100	534	464	499	70	1.0	1044 (950) ^a	94	-154	3.0	-572	521 ^b	124	0.4
200	534	462	498	72	1.0	1044 (950) ^a	94	-152	4.2	-584	524	128	0.5
300	536	460	498	76	1.0	1044 (946) ^a	98	-155	5.0	-586	524	132	0.5
400	538	458	498	80	1.0	1046 (944) ^a	102	167	5.7	-588	524	142	0.5
500	540	456	498	84	1.0	1048 (942) ^a	106	166	6.4	-590	524	142	0.5
1000	544	452	498	92	1.0	1050 (940) ^a	110	175	8.9	-598	527	142	0.5

^a E_{pc_2} values are given in parenthesis. NA - Not appeared

Fig. 5. CVs of complex species in 1 : 2 : 1 Cu^{II}-Et₂dte-phen system (a) and (b) at 100 mV s⁻¹ in acetone containing 0.2 M NaClO₄.

Table 6. Electronic absorption spectral data for binary and mixed-ligand Cu^{II} complex species formed in different molar ratios in acetone medium

Sl no.	System	Ratio	Colour	λ_{\max} (nm)	$\bar{\nu}_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)	ϵ (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Band assignments
1.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dte	1 : 1	Dark green	639	15649	350	d-d
				419	23866	72000	CT
2.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dte	1 : 2	Dark brown	433	23094	8400	CT
3.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : bipy	1 : 1	Light blue	706	14164	100	d-d
4.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : phen	1 : 1	Light blue	735	13605	30	d-d
5.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : phen	1 : 2	Light blue	703	14224	50	d-d
6.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dte : bipy	1 : 1 : 1	Dark brown	640	15625	250	d-d
				380	26315	6300	CT
7.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dte : bipy	1 : 1 : 2	Dark brown	642	15575	200	d-d
				379	26385	5300	CT
8.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dte : bipy	1 : 2 : 1	Dark brown	606	16501	230	d-d
				433	23094	9300	CT
9.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dte : phen	1 : 1 : 1	Dark brown	640	15625	290	d-d
				412	24271	4000	CT
10.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dte : phen	1 : 1 : 2	Dark brown	641	15575	200	d-d
				404	24752	5300	CT
11.	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dte : phen	1 : 2 : 1	Dark brown	624	16025	350	d-d
				424	23584	12000	CT

exhibited weak broad bands at 735 and 703 nm, respectively indicating a distorted octahedral coordination geometry of the complex species in acetone solution.

The electronic spectra of 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 1 : 2 systems exhibited weak absorption bands at ≈ 641 and at ≈ 640 nm for bipy and phen mixed-ligand systems, respectively corresponding to *d-d* transitions and the intense bands at 379 and 407 nm in these two systems are assigned to charge transfer transitions, respectively (Table 6).

The electronic spectra of 1 : 2 : 1 bipy/phen systems exhibited absorption band at 606 and 624 nm corresponding to *d-d* transitions and at 433 and 424 nm is assigned as ligand to metal charge transfer transitions $\text{Et}_2\text{dtc}^- \rightarrow \sigma^*(d_{x^2-y^2})$ of Cu^{II} supporting about the five coordinates binary $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})_2(\text{A})]$ and mixed-ligand $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})(\text{phen})(\text{A})]^+$ species having square-pyramidal geometry in which Cu^{II} ion is coordinated through the four S-atoms in the basal plane and oxygen atom of the solvent molecule (A) along the apical position in the binary complex. In the mixed-ligand complex the metal ion is coordinated via two S-atoms of Et_2dtc^- anion and two N-atoms of phen in the basal plane and the apical position of the square pyramid is occupied by oxygen atom of solvent molecule.

References

1. R. I. Cremllyn, "Pesticides. Preparation and Mode of Action", ed., Wiley, New York, 1978.
2. X. Q. Zeng, J. Li, X. D. Wu, T. H. Ren and W. M. Liu, *Tribology International*, 2007, **40**, 560.
3. A. F. Vanin, A. P. Poltorakov, V. D. Mikoyan, L. N. Kubrina and E. van Faassen, *Nitric Oxide – Biology and Chemistry*, 2007, **15**, 295.
4. M. F. Rabbi, A. Finnegan, L. Al-Harhi, S. Song and K. A. Roebuck, *J. Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndromes Human Retrovirol.*, 1998, **19**, 321.
5. G. Renoux, *Trends Pharm. Sci.*, 1981, **2**, 248.
6. I. A. Mustafa and A. A. Taqa, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2001, **31**, 517.
7. S. A. A. Zaidi, K. S. Siddiqi and N. Islam, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 1197.
8. V. Milacic, D. Chen, L. Ronconi, K. R. Landis-Piwowar, D. Fregona and Q. P. Dou, *Cancer Research*, 2006, **66**, 10478.
9. J. Sharma, Y. P. Singh, R. Bohra and A. K. Rai, *Polyhedron*, 1996, **15**, 1097.
10. T. P. Lockhart, W. F. Manders, E. O. Schlemper and J. J. Zuckerman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **108**, 4074.
11. (a) B. Cvek, V. Milacic, J. Taraba and Q. P. Dou, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **51**, 6256; (b) B. Cvek and Z. Dvorak, *Current Pharm. Design*, 2007, **13**, 000.
12. R. Chant, A. R. Hendrickson, R. L. Martin and N. M. Rohde, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1973, **26**, 2533.
13. A. M. Bond and R. L. Martin, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1984, **54**, 23.
14. (a) H. L. Nigam, K. B. Pandeya, I. P. Tripathi, R. P. Shukla, J. Prasad and K. Srivastava, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 536; (b) K. Srivastava, A. K. Srivastava, D. Porwal and J. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 1195.
15. A. J. Bard and L. R. Faulkner, "Electrochemical Methods : Fundamentals and Applications", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1980, Chap. 11, p. 429.